

(5 plants). All plants were dwarf, irrespective of treatment (Table 1).

When the plants were forwarded to the M₂, the dwarf nature was

maintained, with increase in tiller number and per-plant yield (Table 2).

The dwarf plants were crossed with TKM6 in direct and reciprocal

combinations. The F₁ exhibited the dwarf nature (82.8 cm to 91.3 cm), confirming the dominant nature of the mutation. □

Table 2. Performance of dwarf mutants in M₂. Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Tillers (no.)			Panicle length (cm)			Yield/plant (g)		
	Mean ± SE	Range	CV	Mean ± SE	Range	CV	Mean ± SE	Range	CV	Mean ± SE	Range	CV
5 + 30 kR	80.00±1.33	71.5- 85.0	2.35	9.66±1.15	5-16	16.84	18.24±1.19	17.5-21.4	9.23	13.57±2.29	5.1-28.7	24.04
30 + 5 kR	79.66±0.56	75.5- 81.0	0.99	9.42±0.60	6-12	9.03	20.44±0.48	18.4-22.7	3.32	12.57±1.11	7.6-16.0	12.49
20 + 15 kR	80.11±1.16	75.0- 89.0	2.05	9.33±0.85	8-14	12.88	18.38±0.43	16.4-21.2	3.31	10.37±0.76	7.2-14.9	10.36
control	161.99±0.49	155.0-163.0	0.43	9.40±0.38	8-11	5.12	25.74±0.51	22.5-26.6	2.8	8.73±0.61	7.5-10.3	9.88

TNAU80030 - a promising medium-duration rice for Tamil Nadu

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We evaluated several breeding lines for yield potential and field tolerance for brown planthopper. IR13240-82-2-3-2, a derivative of IR30/ Babawee/ / IR36, was found most promising. It was designated TNAU80030 for testing at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, and was advanced to multilocation trial.

In 10 locations, TNAU80030 ranked first in four and tied with P837 in two

Yield of TNAU80030 in multilocation trials. Tamil Nadu, India, Sep-Oct 1985.

Location	Yield (t/ha)			
	TNAU80030	P837	CO 43	IR20
Aduthurai	4.4	3.9	3.3	3.3
Coimbatore	5.4	4.6	5.2	4.7
Tirur	4.7	4.4	3.2	4.5
Ambasamudram	5.2	5.0	4.7	4.9
Madurai	2.7	2.9	2.5	2.7
Pondicherry	6.4	8.9	6.9	5.8
Tirupathisaram	4.1	2.1	3.6	3.4
Trichy	3.8	4.5	6.6	3.7
Paiyur	5.2	5.1	4.3	4.7
Bhavanisagar	5.1	5.7	5.2	4.4
Mean	4.7	4.7	4.5	4.2

and with CO 43 in one location (see table). TNAU80030 has been advanced to adaptive research trials in farmers' fields.

TNAU80030 is semidwarf with a medium slender grain type and field tolerance for brown planthopper, blast, and rice tungro virus. □

IR18348-36-3-3, a promising rice for irrigated and slight acid sulfate soil in Vietnam

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Table 1. Yield of IR18348-36-3-3 in 1984-86 dry and wet seasons. Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Variety	Dry season			Wet season			Average
	1984	1985	1986	1983	1984	1985	
IR18348-36-3-3 (OM89)	5.5	5.4	5.4	6.1	5.6	5.3	5.5
NN3A (check)	4.4	5.5	5.3	4.8	5.7	4.3	4.9
NN6A (check)	4.8	5.3	5.2	5.2	5.6	5.5	5.2
cv (%)	24.5	—	20.4	13.3	—	26.8	1.3
LSD 5%	1.9		0.6	1.1		0.5	0.2

IR18348-36-3-3, a cross of IR5657-33-2-2 and IR2061-425-1-5-5, was selected at CLRRI from the International Rice Yield Nursery in early 1983. It has 100-115 d maturity, 95-110 cm height, and good grain quality, and is suitable for irrigated, slight acid sulfate soils.

Table 2. Reaction of IR18348-36-3-3 to insects and diseases at CLRRI.

Variety	Reaction ^a to			
	BPH	B1	BB	ShB
IR18348-36-3-3 (OM89)	3-5	4-5	5-7	7
NN6A	3	7-9	7	7
NN3A	3	7-9	7	7
Resistant check ^b	3	1	2	3
Susceptible check ^c	9	9	8	7

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice scale. ^b Resistant check was IR36 for brown planthopper (BPH), IR8 for blast (B1), Compo-selak for bacterial blight (BB), Tapochoz for sheath blight (ShB). ^c Susceptible check was TN1 for BPH, NN7A for B1, IR8 for BB, and IR36 for ShB.